

APPARENT SOUND TRANSMISSION OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The work outlined here discusses the development of a computer based design aid for the evaluation of acoustic performance of honeycomb sandwich composite panels. The methodology is based on an apparent sound transmission loss model (ASTL) which utilises the theoretical approach to sound transmission loss. Modelling was conducted to assess the individual and combined effect of varying the facing (outer skin) thickness, sandwich core thickness and honeycomb cell size on the ASTL of the panels. These parameters can be optimised and so provide the designer accurate guidelines for achieving appropriate sound reduction in specific situations over a range of sound frequencies. Comparison of these results were undertaken with aluminium panels and glass sandwiches

INTRODUCTION

Over the last 40 years, there has been a dramatic increases in the application of lightweight structures for transport vehicles in general use. This has come about as a result of the introduction of the much improved technology in both the manufacturing and design field. In particular, honeycomb sandwich panels are being increasingly used in land, sea and air transport vehicles as major structural components[1,2]. A structural panel consists of an aluminium skin with a honeycomb core and is often utilised in structures to impart lightness and stiffness whilst providing adequate shear strength. Apart from their strength characteristics an oft needed requirement is that the panels provide sound (acoustic) insulation. This is a demand placed by society for the comfort and well being of personnel who work partitioned rooms and travel in various forms of land transport and rail vehicles. Consequently, acoustic performance requirements for a variety of structural materials and environments have been developed by standard codes and regulations[3]

There are readily available theories and experimental data available for the mechanical and structural properties of honeycomb sandwich composite panels together with associated computer software[4] to guide the structural engineer in achieving correct designs. However, the determination of sound insulation (or transmission) in the form of air-borne sound is generally achieved by laboratory or in situ testing.

Theoretical prediction of transmission loss (TL) of sound for composite sandwich panels has been undertaken to a limited extent[5,6] because of the complexity of the procedures involved and the many unknown variables associated with its determination. Bies and Hanse [7] offered a straightforward solution which is useful as a primary tool for estimating TL for different building materials. This simplified approach however does not enable a designer to compare the TL of a sandwich composite to another. Brekke [8] developed a method for calculating sound transmission loss for double and triple partitions known as the Statistical Energy Analysis (SEA). This was based on calculating the energy flow between connected resonant structures. However, no attempt has been made to use this approach on sandwich composites, and lack of existing values for the variables used in this approach make this method difficult to use. The determination of sound TL is generally obtained through laboratory testing, as described in Australian standards[3]. This is particularly true for complex configurations of panels such as sandwich honeycomb panels constructions. Beranek [9], offered a solution by analysing the panel as though it were homogeneous and isotropic.

The aim of this work was to develop a computer aided tool for the analysis and prediction of the acoustic properties of aluminium honeycomb sandwich panels, and to predict the effects on sound transmission loss (STL) of skin thickness, core thickness, and core cell size. An apparent sound transmission loss parameter (ASTL) is defined in terms of the basic mathematical formulations without modifications. The formulation of the calculations used in HONEYCOMB was based on the theories and derivations detailed by Beranek. A comparison with an industrial experimental program was undertaken. Past experiences from industry[10] had shown that the sound transmission loss result can vary by as much as 20 dB from that predicted by theory, even though the test was conducted under standard conditions and procedures.

SANDWICH PANELS

STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

Structural sandwich construction (SSC) involving honeycomb cores (SSHC) include land and space vehicles, yachts, and buildings. A typical SSHC consists of three components, (i) a pair of thin, strong facings or skins, (ii) a thick, lightweight core which separates the facings and carries loads from one skin to the other, and (iii) an adhesive layer between the facings and the core, which constrains them to act as one continuous structure, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a typical sandwich honeycomb structural composite

A variety of materials are used for either the skins or the core of the SSHC. Common skin materials include aluminium, steel, glass fibre and carbon fibre reinforced thermosets. The core is either a foam or a honeycomb layer. The major function of the facings, or the skins, is often to provide the required bending and in-plane shear stiffness and to carry the various loadings together with the ability to minimise noise transmission through the structure..

SOUND TRANSMISSION LOSS

One of the primary requirements for non-structural applications of SSHC is sound reduction.. A common measure of acoustic performance is the sound transmission loss (STL) through a wall or panel. It is a measure of the amount of sound loss whilst travelling from a region where there is a source of air-borne sound through a barrier such as a partition to a region where there is an observer of air-borne sound. The transmission loss of a panel may be defined as the difference between the incident sound level and transmitted sound level, and is in general given by[9],

$$STL = 10 \log_{10} [1/\tau] \quad \text{dB} \quad [1]$$

where, τ = sound transmission coefficient of the wall and is defined as the ratio of transmitted sound pressure to the incident sound pressure.

Because of the many variables involved in determining the STL, an apparent sound transmission loss (ASTL) parameter is utilised as an approximation to the theoretical parameter. The software program designated HONEYCOMB was developed to calculate the apparent STL for sandwich honeycomb panels. The software was then used as a tool to determine the effect of varying the configurations of the sandwich panel on apparent sound transmission loss and so provide the acoustic designer an approximation to field data. For modelling purposes, an apparent sound the transmission loss parameter is developed according to one of two approaches the normal incidence limp wall mass law approach, and the field incidence law [10,12]

Normal Incidence Limp Wall Mass Law

In predicting sound TL, the panel may be described as "limp" (viz. homogeneous and isotropic) over a specific frequency range. The incident sound waves are assumed to impinge on the panel at normal incidence, then the so-called "normal-incidence, limp wall mass law" [12] is

$$STL_O = 10 \log_{10} [1 + (\omega M_s / 2\rho c)^2] \quad \text{dB} \quad [2]$$

which is dependent on the frequency of sound, ω , the speed of sound, c , and material properties of equivalent surface mass, M_s , and density ρ . Thus, allowing a designer to vary the independent material characteristics to determine the acoustic performance for specific conditions.

Field Incidence Law

However, if the sound field modelled is by a diffuse sound field(ie. a group of sound waves of the same average intensity travelling with equally probability in all directions impinging on a wall or panel) then a complex model may be established. Beranek[10] has suggested that an approximate relation of the form is

$$STL_{\text{field}} \cong STL_O - 5 \text{ dB} \quad [3]$$

is appropriate. Additionally if equation (2) is integrated across 90 degrees then an approximation may also be given as a random apparent sound transmission loss (ASTL):

$$ASTL_{\text{random}} = (STL_O) - 10\log_{10} [0.23 (STL_O)] \text{ dB} \quad [4]$$

Although the implementation and development of the HONEYCOMB model allows design with both approaches, the Normal incidence limp wall mass law approach is detailed here.. When utilising honeycomb sandwich panels, it is assumed that the stiffness and mass of the panel is concentrated in the surface sheets, with the core merely serving to hold these sheets apart and the surface mass is an equivalent mass of the total panel..

SOFTWARE DESIGN

HONEYCOMB was written in Turbo Pascal Version 6.0[11].The analysis procedure for ASTL assessment is shown in Fig. 2. where the structural design was determined using an existing program developed by one of the authors SANDWICH [12]]

Figure 2. Outline of analysis steps for determining ASTL of panels

EXAMPLE OF COMPUTER ANALYSIS PROCEDURE :

It is required to design a sandwich honeycomb panel to be fitted into a partition wall in an airport reception lounge. The aim is to have a design which is lightweight, but has the required strength and optimum ASTL characteristic. An initial structural design employing another computer assisted design program, SANDWICH was utilised for this section of the work, and arrived at the following material specification:

- top and bottom skins aluminium, honeycomb aluminium cell core,
- panel length 1000mm width 500mm.: variable cell height,
- variable cell core thickness and skin thickness

Applying the HONEYCOMB model to this structure, the effect of specifying various core cell height, core thickness and exterior skin thickness on the ASTL at various frequencies is shown in Fig.s 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

Varying Core Cell Height

The results of the modelling analysis depicted in Fig. 3 show that increasing the core cell height (size) has little or no effect on the overall ASTL. This is consistent with Eqn (2) which considers the effect of the overall mass on the ASTL. The increase in cell size is equivalent to an increase in mass of less than one per cent overall, and consequently does not contribute significantly to the transmission loss: the TL results are almost equivalent.

Figure 3. ASTL using Normal-Incidence Mass Law, for different Core cell sizes, with top skin = bottom skin = 0.6 mm (

The acoustic designer may essentially consider the cell size as a minor parameter in the overall design process, except for where required, aesthetic purposes

Varying Core Thickness

More than doubling the cell sandwich thickness indicates that there is a small improvement in the sound transmission loss as shown in Fig. 4. consistent with the notion that significant mass changes alter the ASTL as given in Eqn (2).

Figure 4. ASTL using Normal Incidence Mass Law, for different core thicknesses, with top skin = bottom skin = 0.6 mm

Varying Skin Thickness

The results of the modelling analysis depicted Fig. 5 shows that over the frequencies investigated the effect of doubling both the top and bottom skin thickness has resulted in a marked increase in the ASTL. This is expected since the majority of the mass of the panel is concentrated in the outer surfaces and contribute significantly to the sound transmission loss.

Figure 5. ASTL using Normal-Incidence Mass Law, for different skin thicknesses, with top skin thickness = bottom skin thickness.

EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

Experimental comparison with the modelling data was undertaken in cooperation with an industrial organisation [10]. Although the specific details remain confidential, a comparison of their data with the present model is shown in Fig. 6. A composite panel was made from 35.5 mm inner aluminium sandwich core having a 6.5mm diameter cell height with two aluminium skins of 1.6mm on the outer faces, and constrained edges..

Figure 6. Comparison of ASTL obtained using Honeycomb to test data for a sandwich panel with 1.6 mm skins, and 6.5mm cell, and 35.5mm thick core.

The results from the modelling show that ASTL is consistently higher than the measured data, but follows the same trend. This was demonstrated by results obtained using normal-incidence mass law as shown in Fig.6. At the lower frequency range, between 100Hz and 2kHz, the

difference ranges from 5 to 20dB, which is consistent with other reported data[11]. However, over the frequency range 2kHz to 5kHz (as required by standard testing), the difference between the model and the measured data was as high as 25dB indicating that modifications to the theoretical model are required to simulate the overall apparent sound transmission loss behaviour of the composite panel.

Further modelling was carried out to compare these results (using the Normal approach) with experimental data obtained in the industrial project[10]. In this instance, a glass panel sandwich was measured with inner and outer facings of glass 6.5mm and an air sandwich core of thickness 12.7mm. Again, for analysis purposes, the total mass of the panel was assumed to be contained on the surface facings (not an unreasonable approach) since the core was gaseous-air. The results of both the modelling data and the measured are shown in Fig. 7 below. In a similar response to the aluminium honeycomb core sandwich panel, the model predicts values above those that are measured.

Figure 7. Comparison of ASTL calculated using Honeycomb to test data for an airspaced glass, with 6.5mm glass, 12.7mm air space, and 6.5mm glass)

Since wall partitions often have glass windows, particularly in airport lounges and as the sides of an autobus, a combination of both sets of data from the glass and aluminium sandwich provide the acoustic designer with guidelines for the appropriate ratio of glass to aluminium sandwich panel to achieve desired acoustic performance.

CONCLUSION

The theoretical prediction of sound transmission loss is complex and may not provide absolute answers. An apparent sound transmission loss parameter was employed in the development of HONEYCOMB, a computer aided tool for the designer of sandwich honeycomb panels. This may be views as a first step in predicting the acoustic performance of honeycomb sandwich panels. The results of the modelling studies for the aluminium sandwich panels show that:

- the predicted ASTL employing Mass Law theory yields higher but consistent transmission loss values than those from experimental results,
- the ASTL is highly influenced by skin thickness, which is commensurate with the mass being concentrated in the skins of the panel,
- core cell size and thickness has minimal influence on the ASTL, and
- combining the results for the glass sandwich and the aluminium panel provides the acoustic designer guidelines for the design of glass-aluminium panels

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